

1 **BCL11A is a lineage-specifying factor in human breast cancer and marks androgen-negative triple**
2 **negative breast cancer.**

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7 We describe here a nuclear factor whose expression distinguishes androgen receptor (AR)+ and AR-
8 triple negative breast cancers. We identified BCL11A as a lineage-specifying factor in human breast
9 cancer through study of whole transcription in tumors from humans with breast cancer based on molecular
10 subtype. BCL11A was a defining and likely requisite element of the TNBC gene expression signature.
11 Basal-like breast cancer, which possesses significant transcriptional similarity with triple negative breast
12 cancer, was defined by positivity for BCL11A expression (BCL11A+) when compared to luminal A and
13 luminal A subtype tumors in bulk. Triple negative breast cancers could be divided into androgen receptor
14 negative (AR-) and androgen receptor positive (AR+) TNBCs. Studying total transcription in AR+ and AR-
15 triple negative breast cancers revealed that BCL11A was a marker of AR- TNBC, together suggesting
16 BCL11A functioned to specify the hormone receptor negative (HR-) tumor lineage, distinguishing basal
17 and triple negative breast cancers from luminal A and luminal B breast cancers, while actively inhibiting
18 androgen receptor expression. Accordingly, depletion of BCL11A in two human cell types activated
19 expression of AR. BCL11A functions in tumor fate choice during clonal selection, supporting lineage
20 specification of triple negative and basal subtype breast cancers, marking AR- negative TNBC. The data
21 portend to a broader role for nuclear and transcription factors in subtype specification (fate choice) in
22 human breast cancer.
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